

Comparison of Indigenously Prepared Antibiotic Rod and Premade Antibiotic Rod in the Treatment of Infection Following Fracture Fixation

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Abstract:

Infection following fracture fixation is a significant complication that can delay healing and impact patient outcomes. This study compares the efficacy and advantages of an indigenously prepared antibiotic rod versus a commercially available antibiotic rod in treating such infections. A technique with which antibiotic cement-coated interlocking intramedullary nails are prepared in the operating room with the use of nails and materials that generally are available is herein described, clinical outcomes, and potential benefits of the indigenously prepared antibiotic compared to premade antibiotic rod are highlighted. This technique was used in a series of 20 patients in 18 patient goal of union was achieved with control of infection, one patient had persistent nonunion, one had amputation. 2 patient (10%) had cement debonding during removal. control of infection and stability to promote union has traditionally been provided by 2 separate procedures, which have proved to be efficacious in this series with staged approach. Results which showed similar if not greater results with the indigenously prepared antibiotic rod to that of premade antibiotic rod when compared with the available literatures in indexed journals.

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Introduction

Fracture fixation infections present a challenging scenario for orthopedic surgeons. These infections can occur immediately postoperatively or during the course of treatment. The decision between retaining or removing the implant is controversial, and treatment must be individualized to optimize outcomes. Although many surgical options are available, there is no established consensus on the ideal method of treating infection in bone or involving joint replacements. Implanting antibiotic-loaded bone cement is a well-established option [1,2] which is effective in the treatment of osteomyelitis and peri-prosthetic infections. [3,4] This form of treatment allows local delivery of concentrated doses of antibiotics with limited systemic effects. [5,6]

Although antibiotic cement rods have been in used since 1990s, recent studies have shown promising results in the treatment of chronic osteomyelitis and infected nonunions. [5,9] It has also been shown that antibiotic-impregnated cement spacers may be used effectively in these conditions. The ACC rod provides stability while giving high doses of antibiotics to the infected area. This design eliminates the need for external fixation, which can result in higher rates of infection, pain and scarring. [10]

The use of antibiotic rods has gained traction as a method to control infection while providing stability

to the fracture site. This study examines the preparation and efficacy of an indigenously prepared antibiotic rod compared to a commercially available premade antibiotic rod. Bone and joint infections create some of the most challenging circumstances for orthopedic surgeons. Many of these cases are complex in nature, often involving patients with multiple comorbidities who require a prolonged course of treatment. Patients with segmental bone defects, a history of complicated infection, and those with wound/bone healing problems can be especially difficult to treat. Our goal was to use indigenously made antibiotic rod with thorough debridement to eliminate infection and promote bone healing and supplementing with various surgical options to bridge large defects to promote complete union.

Patients and Methods

This study was conducted involving 20 patients with infected fractures treated between 2018 and 2024. This study was a retrospective, non-randomised review of patients from the practice of a single surgeon, who were treated for an infected nonunion, segmental bone defect. Institutional review board approval was obtained. Sample Size is 20 infected fractures, types of Fractures it Included both open and closed diaphyseal fractures & fracture nonunion of long bone. According to ciernymader

classification[12] this study included 17 type B hosts, i.e. patients affected by local or systemic compromising factors and 3 type A hosts who don't have any local or systemic factors.

Patients were accessed clinically and on radiographs and divided into 3 groups based on Treatment approaches taken A) Only Antibiotic Nail. B)Antibiotic Nail + Ilizarov/LRS. C)Staged Procedure (Antibiotic Nail followed by Ilizarov/LRS)

If infection is present and fracture is stable – based on pus and sensitivity antibiotics started for 10 days if no response -debridement and irrigation done, with implant removal. With adequate debridement done if there is minimal mobility at the fracture site as examined on OT table antibiotic nail+ above knee cast with partial or full weight bearing allowed (group A). with adequate debridement but has significant mobility at the fracture site then antibiotic nail + ilizarov / LRS was done (group B). with doubtful debridement we need to open the fracture site and do staged procedure where antibiotic nail was kept for 6 weeks and then followed by fixation using Ilizarov / LRS (group C). All the routine preoperative investigations done and fitness obtained. After thorough debridement and irrigations patient was classified into 3 groups as explained above. Under sterile aseptic conditions antibiotic rod was prepared intraoperatively using , long guide wire, cement, appropriate antibiotics like vancomycin, tobramycin.

After accessing the patient bone anatomy and canal diameter in preoperative radiographs, Antibiotic cement rod were prepared intraoperatively under sterile aseptic condition using 40gm of bone cement powder and culture sensitive antibiotics were used a combination of vancomycin and gentamycin and tobramycin used as broad spectrum antibiotic combination to treat both gram positive and gram-negative organisms we commonly used 3-4 grams of vancomycin 2 to 3 grams of gentamycin nor tobramycin. After mixing antibiotics and dough using binding solution provided mixed till a soft dough was formed , it was then wrapped using long k wire or guide wire. It was then placed inside a pre decided eustachian tube of appropriate size as a mould straightened either ends of the wire were bent which were useful for easy removal later and excess wire was cut. after the bone cement was set ,ET tube was removed. hezorg bend was created for tibial nail and slight anterior curvature was made for femur antibiotic rod. In most cases 9mm or 9.5 or 10mm rods were used.

Based on culture sensitivity appropriate antibiotic were started for six week following surgery. Weight bearing was determined individually based on defect size and soft tissue condition. Patients were admitted

under in patient for 5 to 7 days and were discharged and followed up on outpatient basis at postoperative day 14, 6wks, 9wks, later with monthly follow-up. Radiographs were used to determine the healing of the bone. The bone was considered to have healed once three of four cortices were united and the patient was pain free when bearing full weight. Infection was considered to be eradicated when markers like CSR and ESR returned to normal in the absence of any antibiotic treatment and there were no clinical signs of infection. After healing was recorded, the patients continued to be reviewed every six to 12 months.

Results

Union Time Only Antibiotic Nail .Average union time of 55.77 days. Antibiotic Nail + Ilizarov/LRS. Average union time of 79.12 days. Staged Procedure. Average union time of 102.5 days. Infection Control. Infection was controlled in 19 patients (table no 3) . Union achieved in 17 patients. 2 patient underwent amputation and 1 patient had persistent nonunion.

In group A infection was eliminated in 10 cases. we had 50% cases having excellent and others having good functional bone score (table 4 &5). Mean bone defect size was 1.5cm. one patient had recurrent infection. A positive culture for MRSA was obtained in five patients, for multiple organisms in five patients, and positive for Staphylococcus aureus in one patient.

In group B out of 7 patient which included 3 open ,3 closed and 1 pathological fracture reasonable bone and functional score were achieved (table 4 &5) mean defect size was 3.5cm and LRS or ilizarov helped in immediate weight bearing and patient mobilization. 2 patient underwent amputation one had undergone knee arthrodesis went for above knee amputation, another had chronic infection of ankle and foot and fusion went for below knee amputation. further one patient had short and stiff union treated by shoe raise and physiotherapy due to patient noncompliance.

In group C we achieved 100% union in 2 patient with mean bone gap of 5cm with staged procedure with antibiotic nail and ilizarov.in 2 patient we had partial or full debonding of the cement where additional measures were required to remove debonded cement at the time of extraction of the rod, this was successfully achieved without further complications. Early removal of ABC ROD is motivated to provide definitive fixation or the theoretical consideration that live bacteria are known to persist on antibiotic-impregnated cement under in vitro conditions Connon complications we encountered were nerve compression, painful screw, hematoma joint contractures.

Figure 1: intraoperatively prepared antibiotic rod

Figure 2: SSI of Tibia shaft fracture Patient preoperative, postoperative (6wk) , postoperative (9wk,united)x-rays

Figure 3: preoperative, immediate post operative and post implant removal x-rays of SSI of femur shaft fracture

Figure 4: staged procedure with ilizarov, postop radiograph and clinical picture

Figure 5: femur patient staged procedure with LRS intraop, post-op radiograph

Table 1

	Only Antibiotic Nail	Antibiotic Nail+LRS/Ilizarov	Staged (Antibiotic Nail Followed By LRS/Ilizarov)	Total
Open #	1	3	0	4
Closed#	9	3	2	
Patological #	1	1	0	2
Total	11	7	2	20

Table 2

	Only Antibiotic Nail	Antibiotic Nail+LRS/Ilizarov	Staged (Antibiotic Nail Followed By LRS/Ilizarov)	Total
Femur	5	4	1	10
Tibia	6	3	1	10
Total	11	7	2	

Table 3

	Only Antibiotic Nail		Antibiotic Nail+LRS/Ilizarov		Antibiotic Nail+LRS/Ilizarov	
	Femur(4PTS)	Tibia(6 PTS)	Femur (4 PTS)	Tibia(1 PT)	Femur	Femur
Union-Time (AVG) Days	58.75	52.8	86.2	72	85	120
		55.7	79.1		102.5	

Table 4

	Only Antibiotic Nail	Antibiotic Nail+LRS/Ilizarov	Staged (Antibiotic Nail Followed By LRS/Ilizarov)	Total
Excellent	5	3	1	9
Good	5	1	1(shortening)	7
Fair		1(short+stiff)		1
Poor	1(nonunion)	2(amputation)		3

Table 5

	Only Antibiotic Nail	Antibiotic Nail+LRS/Ilizarov	Staged (Antibiotic Nail Followed By LRS/Ilizarov)	Total
Excellent	6	3	2	11
Good	5	1		6
Fair		1		1
Poor		2(amputation)		2

Discussion

The use of indigenously prepared antibiotic rods demonstrated comparable, if not superior, outcomes to premade antibiotic rods in terms of infection control and bone union. The ability to customize the rod

to patient-specific needs and the cost-effectiveness of the indigenous method are significant advantages. Furthermore, the indigenous method provides flexibility in antibiotic choice and concentration, potentially allowing for more effective treatment tailored

to the patient's specific infection profile. Our results support the findings of our two previously published series. [8,9] The initial series by Those and Conway [9] demonstrated a rate of union of 85% and a rate of eradication of infection of 95%. One patient out of 20 went on to amputation. In the second larger series by the same authors [8] consisting of 52 patients, the rate of union was 84% (41/49), and this increased to 90% (44/49) when patients with a stable nonunion were included (two patients were lost to follow-up, and one patient with a cement spacer was excluded from this calculation). The infection was controlled in 85% (44/52) of patients. Of these patients, 40/52 (77%) only required one intervention with an ACC rod to treat the infected nonunion. Two of these 52 patients underwent amputation, representing a rate of limb salvage of 96%, in their next series which included patients previously reported, [8,9] continues to support the use of this technique as an effective procedure to eradicate infection and support bone healing, with a rate of limb salvage of 95% at a mean follow-up of 34 months. Patients with one procedure decreased from the original 77% to 58%. [8,9] This may be a function of the technique being used in more complicated cases, namely those with segmental bone defects, as the senior surgeon (JC) became more confident with the technique. Bhadra and Roberts [10] described 30 patients in whom, ACC rods were used to treat fractures of the long bone, which had initially been treated with external fixation for more than two weeks, or who had developed osteomyelitis. They used a non-locked Enders nails (Smith & Nephew) coated with antibiotics, which were subsequently exchanged for standard interlocking rods after the infection or pin tracts from the external fixation were healed. The ACC rod was used only to eradicate infection, and not for stability. They recorded difficulty when removing the ACC rods but did not document the number of rods that debonded upon removal. This was a complication we encountered with 2 of the 20 rods that were removed. Technically, this problem can, however, be minimized by over-reaming by 2 mm when introducing the rod, and carefully removing all bone and soft-tissue from the tip of the rod prior to removal. We have used staged procedure of LRS and ilizarov effectively after thorough clinical and radiological examination. In our publication we mention the way to choose proper fixation method and staged procedures gave good results in cases with significant bone defects. Commercially Available Rod Typically made from standardized materials with a uniform distribution of antibiotics. Availability sometimes is an issue as it may require ordering and shipping time. Cost Generally higher due to manufacturing and branding. But our indigenously made antibiotic had comparable efficacy and similar results as the above studies having advantages of, Customization- The rod can be tailored to fit the patient's

specific anatomical needs. Cost-Effective Lower costs compared to commercially available options. Immediate Availability Can be prepared on-site, reducing waiting times for commercially available products. Accessibility – can be done even in low cost settings and periphery and has low learning curve all these make it a good alternative to antibiotic rods available in market.

Conclusion

Indigenously prepared antibiotic rods offer a viable and often advantageous alternative to commercially available premade antibiotic rods for the treatment of infections following fracture fixation. They provide a cost-effective, customizable solution that can be immediately available, potentially improving patient outcomes by reducing infection rates and promoting faster bone union.

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